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ABSTRACTS

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Integrated approach for simulating, optimizing, and fabricating low-cost passive micromixers for enhanced biochemical reactions

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Abstract: This study presents a comprehensive approach to passive micromixer fabrication by leveraging acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) scaffolding to realize diverse geometric configurations. As passive micromixers are crucial in microscale applications, various geometries, such as serpentine, zigzag, square-shaped structures were explored. The study focused on the interplay between geometric structure and mixing efficiency across varying concentrations of reagents. The mixing index was systematically calculated for diverse channel geometries, providing insights into their performance. The research included a detailed analysis using COMSOL Multiphysics to optimize micromixer designs for enhanced mixing efficiency. Notably, the study introduced a curved serpentine pattern as the selected micromixer geometry within a microfluidic chip. The effectiveness of this design was demonstrated through a graphical representation illustrating the mixing efficiency of fluids after every 2 turns of the micromixer. Furthermore, the investigation addresses the cost-effectiveness of the fabrication process, emphasizing a low-cost approach using ABS scaffolding and soft lithographic techniques in limited laboratory setups. Experimental results showcase the successful fabrication of passive micromixers with diverse geometries, highlighting the versatility of the ABS scaffolding approach. This study underscores the significance of ABS scaffolding as a robust substrate for passive micromixer fabrication and emphasizes the importance of computational simulations in guiding design choices for enhanced mixing performance. The findings contribute to the development of customizable and efficient micromixers for applications in chemical synthesis, biotechnology, and diagnostics.

Keywords: ABS scaffolding, COMSOL Multiphysics, microfluidics, passive micromixers, soft lithography.

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